

FOOD IN FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE REPRESENT THE SAFETY OF THE PRODUCTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10780930>

ABSTRACT: The importance of the role of food safety in the formation of a healthy lifestyle is discussed in the article today due to the increasing variety of food products, the use of genetic modification technologies in the food industry, and healthy eating due to other reasons. It is stated that the understanding is being undermined.

Key words: Healthy lifestyle, reproductive health, food safety, vitamin and mineral substances, different hormones, strains, fermentation. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the video selector meeting held on measures to improve the primary link of the health care system and create a healthy lifestyle among the population, "How much through proper nutrition and physical activity- "Everyone should understand how many diseases can be prevented and people's lives can be saved," he said.

Prevention of diseases, mass struggle against hypodynamia-inactivity, involvement of a wide segment of the population, especially young people, in physical education and sports are important factors of health and longevity.

- Of course. Healthy lifestyle consists of four separate programs. The first is to eat wisely. Everyone must eat five meals a day, on time and properly. The second is physical activity. Everyone should have a physical activity program for themselves. Depending on the condition of the body, it is recommended for someone to walk every day, for someone to swim.

The third is mental and emotional health. In this case, every healthy person uses an individual anti-stress program. According to the program, a person's emotions are strictly controlled. It is determined what makes him excited or how he does less mental stress, and useful recommendations are made taking this into account.

The fourth is reproductive health. According to this program, women's health is thoroughly checked before becoming pregnant. Recommendations are given about the time to have children and how many children they can have during their lifetime.

- You said that one of the main factors that make up the essence of a healthy lifestyle is rational nutrition. Today, due to the increasing variety of food

products, the use of genetic modification technologies in the food industry, and other reasons, the concept of healthy eating is being undermined. — Proper nutrition is represented by a balance between consumed and expended energy. The main part of the energy generated from the daily average food consumption should be spent during the day. Taking into account physical activity and professional work, it is necessary to strictly observe the norm of eating caloric foods. If the consumed energy is not replaced, i.e., if the diet is violated, a person may become weak or become fat. A person who eats high-quality food rich in vitamins and minerals at the right time is in a good mood and is healthy. This will have a positive effect on his lifestyle, family and career.

The interval between meals should not exceed 3-4 hours, it is necessary to eat food in small quantities and not to be too full, to get used to getting up from food with a light appetite. It is advisable to eat food in the same order throughout the day. When eating in a hurry, a person eats more than he needs. Because the feeling of satiety reaches the central nervous system slowly. The feeling of satiety occurs when blood glucose and amino acids reach sufficient levels. A certain ratio of proteins, fats and carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals is necessary for the normal vital activity of the human body. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay attention to combinations of nutrients when determining the diet.

It is very important to check the safety of food products, to clarify that they meet sanitary and hygienic requirements. Studying the safety of consumed food products should be the duty of every citizen.

Achieving a normal weight, putting an end to excessive and disordered eating, eating the right amount of protein, fat, carbohydrate, mineral and vitamin rich foods are important factors of health.

- If you also dwell on the importance of physical exercises. - Why do physical exercises? The most important reason is to improve the quality of life. Exercises and any physical activity not only relieve stress, but also improve the condition of the body and prolong life.

In addition, physical activity is an important aspect of body weight control for three reasons: it accelerates weight loss by burning calories in the body, it helps the absorption of the fat layer accumulated in the body and increases muscle mass, it shifts the focus from food to physical activity. directs to activity. According to the results of recent years' research, proper nutrition not only reduces excess weight, but also lowers arterial blood pressure and reduces blood sugar. This is very important for diabetic patients. It also strengthens the

cardiovascular system, prevents premature aging and eliminates serious diseases such as myocardial infarction and stroke. CONCLUSION: A healthy lifestyle lays the foundation for the development of various aspects of human life, long life and full fulfillment of social duties, active participation in forms of life such as work, collective, family life. healthy lifestyle is manifested as a specific form of human activity aimed at maintaining, strengthening and improving one's health.

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